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The Lost Diamond of Süleyman the Magnificent

By Anna Malecka

Since the 19th century, writers on gems have mentioned a diamond of about 147 carats that was in the treasury of the Turkish sultans, referring to it as the Ottoman or Turkey I. These authors state unanimously that the fate of this stone, one of the largest diamonds from the Muslim world, is unknown.

Prior to 1739, when Nadir Shah of Persia pillaged the Mughal treasury leading to a flood of large gemstones onto the market, the Ottoman was not only the largest diamond in the Istanbul treasury but also the second largest worked diamond recorded outside India. The largest, weighing about 453 metric carats, was to be found in the possession of Shah Safi II of Persia.

The earliest record noting the Ottoman is a letter dated to February 1533 written by a Venetian resident in Istanbul. He describes a pure diamond weighing 144 carats (most probably Venetian) or about 149 metric carats, in the possession of Sultan Süleyman the Magnificent (r.1520-1566), calling it 'exquisite', possibly indicating that it had been cut. The stone was acquired as a rough in the Indian city of Bijapur at a cost of 30,000 pieces of gold, eventually being purchased by the Sultan for 100,000 Venetian ducats, after having been brought to Istanbul by the Persian gem merchant Khwaja Muhammad al-Kashani.

The Ottoman was still in the Istanbul treasury at the beginning of the 18th century. It was possibly the same stone shown worn in the egret of Sultan Mustafa II (r.1695-1703), an oval, probably rose-cut diamond with a weight described as 148 carats (fig 1).

There are no eye-witness accounts that attest to the colour

of the stone. A 17th-century story circulated in Europe about how two diamonds – the Ottoman and a yellow diamond, the 'Florentine', from the Medici treasury – originated from the same stone. The stone was cut in two, in order to satisfy the demands of a Muslim and a Christian ruler. The story, though, may have been fabricated to explain the yellow colouring of the Ottoman. A female Russian visitor to the Ottoman treasury at Istanbul in the 1880s noted that the largest diamond was yellowish. While she did not indicate the weight of this stone, she did report that it was the 'size of a walnut'.

It is possible that the Ottoman was still in the Istanbul treasury at the time of Sultan Abdülhamid II (r.1876-1909). When he lost his throne, he was forced to dispose of his diamond collection. In order to make the stone more fashionable, and thus more marketable, it may have been recut and sold. If we accept that the Ottoman was yellow, it is still difficult to identify within the collection since Abdülhamid possessed many stones of this colour. There is one possible candidate: the Sultan Abdülhamid II – a light yellow, antique-cut brilliant weighing 70.54 carats. This was sold by the London jeweller Graff in 1983 to Imelda Marcos, the wife of the then President of the Philippines.

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Fig 1. Detail from Aubry de la Motraye, *Voyages du Sr A. de La Motraye en Europe, Asie et Afrique: ou l'on trouve une grande variété de recherches géographiques, historiques et politiques sur l'Italie, la Grèce, la Turquie, la Tartarie, Crimée et Nogaye la Circassie, la Suède et la Laponie, etc.* (1727), vol. 1, pl. 1. Sultan Mustafa II is shown second from right (d).